

Coronavirus Disease Research Community – COVID-19

ZENODO CERN, May 8th, 2020

Publication date: May 7rd, 2020

Title: **Forecast of COVID19 infections, UK**

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I have updated the COVID19 infections data and forecast in UK on May 7th, publishing the graphs on the following free blogs:

<https://covid19forecast.blogspot.com/>

<https://euocovid19.blogspot.com/>

The same figures are reported here on May 8th, 2020.

The forecast of the total positive cases, according to the Verhulst equation is over 240,000 cases, with a ratio per 1000 capita of 3.7, while the forecast of the total deaths is over 34,000.

The data of the new cases are still along a plateau and a forecast of decrease is not yet possible.

The data of the new deaths, on the contrary, are showing a trend to decrease and tomorrow I will make that forecast.